

SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF GLOBAL ECONOMIC TRENDS

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Abstract: The article analyzes the specific characteristics of global economic trends and the processes related to their impact on the economic system of Uzbekistan. Theoretical opinions related to existing problems and ways to eliminate them are presented.

Key words: Globalization, modern trends, economic system, integration, modernization, diversification.

Today, the identification of modern global economic trends, the study and analysis of their characteristic features are gaining urgent importance for scientists all over the world. Determining the impact of global trends on the lives of different peoples and the economic system of states is an important issue and a serious problem at the same time. Based on these reasons, it is necessary to be able to correctly assess the influence of trends of global significance in the effective solution of these problems, the determination of the country's national economic development models, the provision of economic security, and the rational solution of existing problems. Because life itself and the demands of the people are putting before us new and more complex tasks that need to be found in practical solutions [1]. Faster resolution of these problems and the complex tasks that life itself has set before us, finding their solutions, in many ways affect the economic level of people, especially the content of market economy relations, their requirements, conflicting and confusing features, laws and regulations in our country. It depends on their deeper understanding of the content of the strategic programs adopted in order to accelerate economic development, the deepening of the wide-scale economic reforms that are being implemented, the priority of human interests, the purpose and essence of economic liberalization, structural change, modernization and diversification.

Fundamental institutional and structural changes are being implemented in the economy based on the concept of a unique way of transition to a market economy developed in our country, ownership relations are being revised based on the reorganization of production and privatization of state-owned enterprises, new market mechanisms and market infrastructure is being formed. At the same time, the republic's entry into the 21st century coincided with the strengthening of the world trends of globalization on the basis of economic

integration, which places high demands on national systems. Globalization limits, but by no means eliminates, the exercise of economic policy dominance by states. Further strengthening of macroeconomic stability and maintaining high rates of economic growth, including ensuring that the State budget is balanced at all levels, the national currency and the price level in the domestic market are stable today remain the most important priority tasks. Today, the national economy of Uzbekistan, as an integral element of the global economy, is changing and developing in harmony with it. Therefore, the positive trends characteristic of the global economy are also evident in the conditions of Uzbekistan. In particular, on the one hand, as in all countries, the national economy is being liberalized in Uzbekistan, its relations with other economies are intensifying, the possibilities of using the potential of international economic and financial organizations, and receiving economic assistance are expanding. On the other hand, economic protectionism, which is growing in the world, hinders the increase of Uzbekistan's export potential. The high volatility of prices in the world market has a serious impact on the volume of exports and imports of the country, and on the consumer market. Entrepreneurship is one of the activities that became a reality after our country gained independence. However, this does not lead to the conclusion that entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan will be resolved only in the next 30 years. There have been successful entrepreneurs throughout the ages. Moreover, the passage of the Great Silk Road through the territory of the country, and the fact that Central Asia has always been an important link in world trade relations, has led to the rapid development of entrepreneurship. The implementation of socialist ownership and production during the years of Soviet power also put an end to entrepreneurship in the country. The situation changed positively only after the independence of Uzbekistan. During the years of independence, serious attention was paid to the development of entrepreneurship. As a result of this attention, for example, by 2015, "the number of people employed in small business entities has exceeded 10.2 million people. This makes up 77.9% of the total employed people in the economy. Their share in the gross domestic product of our country reached 56.5% from 38.2% in 2005. The share of small business in the production of industrial products was 38.9 percent, and in export 26.9 percent." [2;21]. However, in recent years, despite the fact that great attention has been paid to the development of entrepreneurship in our country, including the creation of conditions for young men and women to engage in entrepreneurship, some problems that are an obstacle to this activity remain.

The existence of these problems in some cases causes young people to hesitate and take risks in doing business. As a result, the possibilities of entrepreneurial activity to optimize the lifestyle of young people are not fully realized. Therefore, in order to develop youth entrepreneurship and therefore fundamentally change their lifestyles, it is necessary to focus on eliminating these problems. When talking about the measures to be implemented in this regard, first of all, it is necessary to mention the need to eliminate corrupt situations that are an obstacle to business activity. In general, today corruption remains an obstacle to entrepreneurship in all countries of the world and worsens the investment environment. "According to the analysis, this disease damages the world economy by an average of 2.6 trillion dollars every year" [3]. Unfortunately, our country has yet to get rid of this evil. It is widely encountered in various spheres of social life, including business activities. "Entrepreneurs are still faced with corruption in areas such as land allocation, cadastre, construction, license, customs, banking, state procurement, as evidenced by many appeals to the President, as well as by the press and social networks"[4;42] . According to the results of the survey conducted by the Agency for Combating Corruption of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 69% of the entrepreneurs who participated in the survey still face corrupt situations [5].

No matter how far we are from a global perspective, which is above any border, the role of states has changed in several directions. Although states have the ability to attract and retain capital and conduct independent economic policies, their role is not to control, but to regulate the economy.

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